

Conference Abstract

Can we trust multispectral drone datasets for eLTER variables monitoring? Sensors sensitivity and applications.

Thibaut Peres^{‡,§}, Jean Nabucet^{‡,§}, Julien Pellen^{‡,§}, Tanguy Doare^{‡,§}, Thomas Houet^{‡,§}

[‡] UMR LETG, CNRS Université de Rennes 2, Rennes, France

[§] LTSER-FR Zone Atelier Armorique, Rennes, France

Corresponding author: Thomas Houet (thomas.houet@univ-rennes2.fr)

Received: 31 Jan 2025 | Published: 28 May 2025

Citation: Peres T, Nabucet J, Pellen J, Doare T, Houet T (2025) Can we trust multispectral drone datasets for eLTER variables monitoring? Sensors sensitivity and applications. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e148427.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e148427>

Abstract

Multispectral drone data are widely used for monitoring vegetated critical zones. Numerous indices derived from remotely sensed data provide objective and spatially comprehensive observations of land surfaces. These indices are employed in various applications, including precision agriculture (Deng et al. 2018), water stress detection in viticulture (Santesteban et al. 2017; Kandylakis et al. 2020), forest ecology for phenology and health assessment (Ecke et al. 2024, Fraser and Congalton 2021), ecosystem habitat mapping (Alvarez-Vanhard et al. 2020), and soil moisture monitoring (Bertalan et al. 2022). In all these cases, vegetation indices remain fundamental tools for vegetation monitoring.

Most studies rely on reflectance data from multispectral sensors calibrated using manufacturer-provided reference panels. These 'plug-and-play' solutions facilitate widespread applications, yet reflectance values are rarely validated against ground-truth spectral signatures. Consequently, users often place unquestioning trust in pre-processed data. Additionally, spectral bands vary across different sensors, much like satellite sensors, further complicating data consistency.

This study presents the results of a calibration and validation experiment. Four multispectral sensors (Parrot Sequoia, Micasense Dual MX and Altum-PT, and Spectral Device) with distinct spectral characteristics (spatial and spectral resolution, bandwidth) were compared with spectral signatures obtained using an ASD Fieldspec Pro spectroradiometer. Spectral data were collected along transects in the Sougéal marsh (N 48°51', W -1°50', France), which features diverse herbaceous habitats and varying soil moisture conditions (Fig. 1). The comparison highlights sensor sensitivity and their capacity to provide consistent data. Preliminary results indicate significant quality differences between sensors.

Figure 1. [doi](#)

UAV multispectral image (NIR-R-G color composite) of the Sougéal marsh with spectroradiometer and soil moisture in situ measurement (blue dots).

Two applications were conducted. The first analyzed NDVI derived from NIR and red bands to evaluate how spectral characteristics and sensitivity impact this commonly used vegetation index. The second application focused on soil moisture monitoring. One sensor, equipped with SWIR bands, was used to estimate soil moisture using the OPRAM model (Sadeghi et al. 2017). Index values were compared against in situ spectral signatures and soil moisture measurements obtained with a Tetra Probe.

Presenting author

Thibaut Peres

Presented at

POSTER

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Alvarez-Vanhard E, Houet T, Mony C, Lecoq L, Corpetti T (2020) Can UAVs fill the gap between in situ surveys and satellites for habitat mapping? *Remote Sensing of Environment* 243 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.111780>
- Bertalan L, Holb I, Pataki A, Négyesi G, Szabó G, Kupásné Szalóki A, Szabó S (2022) UAV-based multispectral and thermal cameras to predict soil water content – A machine learning approach. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 200 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2022.107262>
- Deng L, Mao Z, Li X, Hu Z, Duan F, Yan Y (2018) UAV-based multispectral remote sensing for precision agriculture: A comparison between different cameras. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 146: 124-136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.09.008>
- Ecke S, Stehr F, Frey J, Tiede D, Dempewolf J, Klemmt H, Endres E, Seifert T (2024) Towards operational UAV-based forest health monitoring: Species identification and crown condition assessment by means of deep learning. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 219 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2024.108785>
- Fraser B, Congalton R (2021) Monitoring Fine-Scale Forest Health Using Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) Multispectral Models. *Remote Sensing* 13 (23). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13234873>
- Kandyllakis Z, Falagas A, Karakizi C, Karantzas K (2020) Water Stress Estimation in Vineyards from Aerial SWIR and Multispectral UAV Data. *Remote Sensing* 12 (15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12152499>
- Sadeghi M, Babaeian E, Tuller M, Jones S (2017) The optical trapezoid model: A novel approach to remote sensing of soil moisture applied to Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 observations. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 198: 52-68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2017.05.041>
- Santesteban LG, Di Gennaro SF, Herrero-Langreo A, Miranda C, Royo JB, Matese A (2017) High-resolution UAV-based thermal imaging to estimate the instantaneous and seasonal variability of plant water status within a vineyard. *Agricultural Water Management* 183: 49-59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2016.08.026>